

ARCHITECTURE OF THE ROMAN PERIOD

Muhammedyar Alliyarov

Teacher of Karakalpak State University named after Berdak.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10894446>

Abstract. In this article features suitable for Roman architecture are described in terms of appearance, character and psychological impact on a person.

Keywords: memory, architecture, temple, monument, roman period.

АРХИТЕКТУРА РИМСКОГО ПЕРИОДА

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны черты, подходящие для римской архитектуры с точки зрения внешнего вида, характера и психологического воздействия на человека.

Ключевые слова: память, архитектура, храм, памятник, римский период.

Charlemagne's empire did not last long. His decline began during the emperor's lifetime.

After his death, the conflict between his sons and grandsons disturbed the peace of the country.

The attack of armed forces from the surrounding area also brought heavy hardships to the people. From this period, the development of art also increased. Previously built buildings turned into ruins.

Rare architectural monuments were looted or stolen. From the end of the 10th century, Fahat began to trace his life in Europe. Feudal relations were formed in Kupkina lands. The history of art and architecture has entered a new stage. This stage of development, which includes the 10th-11th centuries, is called Romanesque architecture. The term "Romanesque architecture" of this period was used in scientific sources in 1825 by the French archaeologist Arnis Comon as a factor denoting Western European architecture.

During this period, the role of the church in European social life was great. Especially in France, England, Germany, Spain, the great revival and related art forms were created by order of the church. In the Roman period, it occupies the place of architecture. The building in the Romanesque style is somewhat serious and heavy in appearance. Its walls are also thick and strong, its doors, windows and gates are narrow. Columns used for functional and decorative purposes are also rough and rough. These features, which are suitable for Roman architecture, determine the unique appearance, character and psychological impact on a person.

Another feature of Romanesque architecture is the abundance of flat surfaces on its inner walls. This feature creates an opportunity for the development of monumental color image. In the 11th century, this period experienced its heyday. Stained glass also became an integral part of architecture. During this period, sculpture developed in connection with architecture. The ieshtokh, columns and capitals of the building, special shelves on the wall are decorated with sculptural art. Miniatures and small sculptures were also influenced by architecture. The Roman style of architecture had a great influence on the construction of the fuhoro.

The term "Romanesque" is conditional, derived from the Latin word "Roman", and it is assumed that the architecture of this period used forms widely used in Roman architecture.

Romanesque architecture developed based on the achievements of the Carolingian period.

It caused the emergence and competition of many local schools in Romanesque architecture.

No matter how diverse these schools are, it cannot be denied that they are based on a single principle. This situation is seen in the nature of decorative forms in the plan and construction. The buildings of this period were made of stone, and the basilica type took the main place in the construction, but unlike the previous period, the basilica had more than two transepts, and the commentary part of the building (choir) reserved for church servants and priests was expanded, and additional rooms and basements were built.

The unique aspect of Roman architecture is the closing of the roof in the form of a curved arched dome and the placement of windows. This construction technique is becoming more and more perfect. Columns and capitals used in architecture. In the advanced period of Romanesque architecture, capitals and columns took on a unique sculptural appearance. By this century, there appeared a separate house-type palace where the feudal lord lived. Usually, there is a large courtyard of the castle, in the upper part of which a tall and tall tower-like building is built, which consists of many rooms where the feudal lord lives.

The outskirts of the city are surrounded by a thick wall. Built buildings were few and simple. The visual art of the novel is also unique and concrete. The leading place in the art of this period is occupied by sculpture, first of all, carved images. It conveys great content to the audience, directly viewed as architectural elements. In the period of the early Romanesque, the sculptures of the 10th century were adapted to architectural forms. By the 12th century, the capital became a well-known system of decoration of the architectural ensemble. France is the classic homeland of feudalism in the country.

During the heyday of medieval art, his art occupies a leading position in Western Europe.

In French architecture, the unique aspects of the Roman style are clearly visible. French architecture, which is colorful in terms of its decorative decoration and constructive structure, occupies an important place in the art of European construction. The types of architecture created here became a model for imitation in many European cities. The 11th-12th century temple of the grant in Poitou shows features typical of the Romanesque style. It is somewhat low in appearance, the stone walls are made thick and solid. Small narrow windows left during these periods increase the thickness of these walls and increase its restraint. This temple consists of three naves. The upper nave is slightly higher than the two side naves, and the sun shines in through the small windows. The walls of the building are decorated with architectural decorative elements of the type of sculptures. There are shelves on the second and third floors, and the used semi-columns, semi-circular arches, etc., with statues placed inside them, add grace to the serious appearance of the building. The architectural monument reflects the political situation of that time.

In the temples built in Burgundy, a desire to change their forms is felt. This feature is especially noticeable in the church in Cluny. This church was built at the end of the 11th century.

At that time, it was one of the largest temples in Europe. The principles of this building, which was destroyed at the beginning of the 19th century, are used as the basis for many churches.

This temple with five naves is characterized by the rhythmicity of the external elements, the complete appearance of the volumes, and the appearance and harmony of the fine details.

Romanesque buildings built in Germany are characterized by their clear cubic forms and the grandeur of their appearance.

The abundance of light towers ensures its dynamic appearance. Lenses on a flat wall surface serve to give the building a dynamic appearance, in this respect the cathedral in Vermos is characteristic. Italy has a stylistic unity in the architecture of this country. Therefore, in some of its areas, the influence of Byzantium is felt, while in others, the traditions of Romanesque architecture can be felt. Early Tuscan and Lombard schools were influenced by local antique traditions. The architectural ensemble of Pisa is noteworthy in this regard. Each bin in the ensemble has improbable value.

Their outer walls are divided into several tiers with elegant arcades. This situation has added lightness and elegant grace to the appearance of the building. As a result, even the huge Pisa Cathedral looks light and attractive. And the elliptical dome provides its harmonious complete appearance.

REFERENCES

1. Alliyarov M. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE GOTHIC PERIOD IS ALSO HISTORICAL //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 182-184.
2. Alliyarov M. Importance of Excavation Work in the Organization and Enrichment of Museums //Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 35-40.
3. Alliyarov M. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE GOTHIC PERIOD IS ALSO HISTORICAL //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 182-184.
4. Alliyarov M. Architecture and The Art of Designing //American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 161-165.
5. Aziza T. TARIXIY ASARLANING JAMIYAT TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN O'RNI: "YULDUZLI TUNLAR" ASARINING BOSH G'OYASI //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 42-46.
6. Tleumuratova A. J. QORAQALPOG'ISTONDA TEATR SAN'ATINING SHAKLLANISHI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR. – 2024.
7. Tleumuratova A. JAHON ANIMATSIYA SAN'ATIDA TARIXIY MAVZU, OBRAZLAR TALQINI VA O'ZBEK ANIMATSIYA SAN'ATIDA TUTGAN O'RNI //ВЕСТИНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА. – 2023. – Т. 61. – №. 3. – С. 221-223.
8. Xojamuratov K. B. THE FOUNDATIONS AND FORMATION OF PAINTING IN THE FINE ARTS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN IN THE 1970S AND 1980S //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 341-345.
9. Xojamuratov Q. B. ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF FINE ARTS IN SCHOOLS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 333-336.
10. Xojamuratov K. B. THE FOUNDATIONS AND FORMATION OF PAINTING IN THE FINE ARTS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN IN THE 1970S AND 1980S //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 341-345.

11. Alliyarov M. Architecture and The Art of Designing //American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 161-165.
12. Alliyarov M. A., Rakhimbaev O. D. MONUMENTAL ARCHITECTURE OF ANCIENT KHOREZM //Матрица научного познания. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 145-152.